

ABSTRACT BOOK

SETAC EUROPE 34TH ANNUAL MEETING

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*SCIENCE-BASED SOLUTIONS IN TIMES OF CRISIS: INTEGRATING SCIENCE
AND POLICY FOR ENVIRONMENTAL CHALLENGES.*

Abstract Book

SETAC Europe 34th Annual Meeting

Table of Contents

About SETAC	3
Abstracts	5
Track 1: Environmental and Human Toxicology: From Molecules to Organisms, From Omics to in Vivo	5
Track 2: Ecotoxicology Becomes Stress Ecology: From Populations to Ecosystems and Landscapes	181
Track 3: Environmental Chemistry and Exposure Assessment: Analysis, Monitoring, Fate and Modeling.....	271
Track 4: Ecological and Human Health Risk Assessment of Chemicals, Mixtures and Stressors and Risk..... Mitigation Strategies	689
Track 5: Life Cycle Assessment and Foot-Printing	858
Track 6: Environmental Policy, Risk Management, and Science Communication.....	961
Track 7: Moving Beyond – Cross Cutting Themes, Emerging and Transdisciplinary Topics.....	1075
Track 8: Special Sessions.....	1106
Author Index	1113

This book compiles the abstracts from the 34th annual meeting of the Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry – Europe (SETAC Europe), conducted from 5–9 May 2024 in Seville, Spain.

The abstracts are reproduced as submitted by the author and accepted by the scientific committee. They appear in order of abstract code and alphabetical order per presentation type. The poster spotlight abstracts are included in the list of poster abstracts. The presenting author of each abstract is highlighted in bold.

The information in this abstract book reflects the status of the abstracts as was on 29 April 2024.

Mining activities, particularly those involving metal extraction, pose a significant risk to aquatic systems due to the potential contamination and accumulation of heavy metals. To mitigate these risks, several strategies can be employed to reduce the discharge and accumulation of heavy metals in aquatic environments. These strategies include organic and inorganic amendments addition, as well as remedial actions such as waste management and recycling to minimize the adverse impact on ecosystem and organisms health. One potential organic amendment is biochar, which has been shown to effectively adsorb heavy metals and reduce their leaching into water systems. Composts and manures can be adequate alternatives, as they can enhance soil fertility and promote the uptake of heavy metals by plants, consequently reducing their availability in aquatic ecosystems. Additionally, inorganic amendments such as zeolites and calcium carbonate are also proposed due to their capacity to trap and immobilize heavy metals. The main goal of this work was to evaluate the impact of the range of soil amendments applied to the mining soil on the soil functioning in contaminant and nutrient retention, using direct ecotoxicity assessment with aquatic bioassays. To study this, we produced the aqueous soil extracts, i.e., elutriates, as a proxy to run-off. The elutriates were produced out of the soil sampled from the field plot experiment - non-amended mining soil, and soil amended with different treatments such as compost, biochar, zeolite, calcium carbonate, and their combinations. Freshwater species from different trophic levels – green algae *Raphidocelis subcapitata*, water flea *Daphnia magna* and zebrafish *Danio rerio* were exposed to these elutriates. The evaluated endpoints were algae growth, water flea immobilization and oxidative stress biomarkers, hatching and mutagenicity of zebrafish. Non-amended mining soil elutriate induced toxicity in all the species. The incorporation of amendments substantially decreased the toxicity of the elutriates of the mining soils, with the responses being treatment dependent. Complementary data analysis of the physicochemical characterization (pH, metals, nutrients, etc.) of the elutriates is ongoing, and overall data integration is expected to provide better insight on the adequacy of different treatments and/or their combinations in terms of reducing the pressure from contaminated mining soil on aquatic ecosystem.

4.01.P-Mo334 Field Aging of a Commercial Biochar: Effect on the Retention of Sulfamethoxazole and Ethofumesate Over Time

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The high mobility of organic pollutants in soils may represent an obstacle to their bioremediation and/or natural attenuation. The addition of adsorbents to soils is an excellent strategy to enhance their retention providing the residence time needed for their degradation by bacteria, fungi, or plants. Biochar (BC), the carbonaceous material produced by pyrolysis of biomass, has been proposed as a soil amendment due to its optimal adsorption properties. However, once in the soil, BCs undergo changes which alter their physicochemical properties and impact their adsorption capacity. Evaluating BC aging under real field conditions is thus crucial to determine its long-term efficiency as an adsorbent. In this work, a commercial BC was aged for one year in the top 0-5 cm of soil plots of an experimental farm located in southern Spain. Unamended and amended soil samples were periodically taken (t = 0, 1, 3, 6, and 12 months) and their retention capacity for the antibiotic sulfamethoxazole and the pesticide ethofumesate was assessed by batch adsorption and leaching experiments. Changes in the physicochemical properties of the BC particles upon aging were evaluated by determining their elemental composition and registering their Fourier-transform infrared spectra and scanning electron micrographs. The results showed that the addition of the BC to the soil greatly increased the adsorption of both compounds compared to unamended soil. However, the adsorption capacity of the adsorbent decreased gradually over time, affecting leaching rates. The characterization of the adsorbent indicated that aging mainly consisted of physical changes at the BC particles' surface. Despite the loss of adsorption capacity of BC over time, one-year aged BC-amended soil samples retained the pollutants to a much greater extent than unamended soil samples. This means that, after one year of residence in the soil, the BC could continue retaining much of the investigated pollutants, which would favor the restoration of the contaminated soil through suitable bioremediation processes. Acknowledgment: Financed by project P20-00746 of Junta de Andalucía (Spain) and projects PID2020-112563RB-I00 and PID2022-137187OB-I00 of the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation, with (EU) FEDER funds.

4.01.P-Mo335 Evaluating the Significance of Two Different Biochar Dissipation Pathways in Soil

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Biochar, as a product derived from the pyrolytic conversion of biomass, can perform several ecosystem functions, two of which are particularly important: long-term soil quality improvement and carbon sequestration. The degree to which these benefits will be realized is largely determined by the stability of the biochar within the soil. Despite generally being considered highly persistent, a mild depletion of biochar stocks, specifically the Pyrogenic C fraction, was observed during a 12-year field experiment set up in Donndorf/Eckersdorf, Germany. Hence, the question arises: can the identified loss over this relatively short time period be attributed to some transformation of biochar, or is it simply the result of its physical transport. To address this question, samples collected from the Donndorf/Eckersdorf trial were analyzed for the amounts of free benzene polycarboxylic acids (BPCAs), as they serve as molecular markers for the degradation of Pyrogenic C. The samples were obtained from two experimental variants: one with the individual application of a high dose of biochar (31.5 t/h), and the other combining biochar (31.5 t/h) with composted material (70 t/h). Sampling was conducted in 2009, prior to the experiment's establishment, and subsequently at two-year intervals in 2013 and 2021. In 2009 and 2013, samples were taken at depths of 0–

10 cm and 10–30 cm, while in 2021, samples were collected at a depth of 0–30 cm. The soil pH ranged from 5.4 to 5.8, and the texture was as follows: 62% sand, 12% silt, and 26% clay. The biochar was produced through the pyrolysis of beech and pine wood chips. The analysis of free BPCAs was conducted using GC-FID. In most of the analyzed soil samples free BPCAs were not detected. In the remaining cases, free BPCAs were identified, at both investigated soil depths, but only in amounts that can be considered relatively low, ranging from 3.96×10^{-5} to 5.51×10^{-2} g/kg. Given that the pH and sandy loam texture of the examined soil did not favor the loss (further oxidation or leaching) of free BPCAs, their absence or low abundance can be considered a clear indication of the high stability of the applied biochar. Therefore, the observed loss of biochar should be attributed to its physical transport. However, as absence or low levels of free BPCAs may also result from the high detection limit of the GC-FID method, to confirm the obtained results, samples will be further analyzed using the LC-VWD.

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4.01.P-Mo336 Effectiveness of a hydrocarbon contaminated soil bioremediation process

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Bioremediation of total petroleum hydrocarbons soil (TPH) can be achieved through various techniques. Bioaugmentation upon injection of selected functional microbial strains, among others, enables immediate degradation. The use of microorganisms that produce surface-active compounds enhances solubility, mobility, bioavailability, and subsequent biodegradation of hydrophobic organic compounds by emulsifying or solubilizing the hydrocarbons.

The evaluation of soil toxicity becomes an additional but fundamental step of the bioremediation process, being an indicator of the success of the biological treatment. In fact, the effectiveness of the bioremediation process cannot be evaluated only through analytical monitoring, which is complex due mainly to the characteristics of the matrix.

In the framework of Italian PNRR project “Return”, the goal of this work was to determine the effectiveness of a microbial formula in soil TPH bioremediation by pollutant biodegradability assessment and the toxic effects attenuation with an approach that involves chemical, microbiological, respirometry and ecotoxicological evaluation.

This work started with the selection of microorganisms for biosurfactant production using 50 aerobic bacterial strains from the ENEA-MIRRI Microbial Collection. The strains were grown on selective liquid media (BDH) and the surfactant production was followed up to 10 days using Oil Spreading Assay and E24 assay on the supernatants, to test their capacity to produce biosurfactant. The best biosurfactant producers, (i.e. A2-5 *Pseudomonas glycinis*, OSS19 *Rhodococcus qingshengi*, SM41, *Kokuria polaris*, SME 2.4 *Arthrobacter humicola*, SME 2.18 *Microbacterium hydrocarbonoxydans*) were further investigated. Cross-streak tests among strains were performed to check the compatible strains to be pooled to set-up the formula for bioaugmentation in biometer flasks.

Ecotoxicological tests were carried out on either the solid fraction and aqueous and organic extract of TPH soil at different bioremediation stages. Root elongation toxicity test with *Lepidium sativum*, *Sinapis alba* and *Sorgum saccharatum* assessed toxic effect directly in soil fraction. The bacteria *Aliivibrio fischeri* and the crustacean *Daphnia magna* were used to assess the acute toxicity of leachates while a chronic test was performed with the algae *Raphidocelis subcapitata*. The combined use of these test organisms proved to be a viable tool for demonstrating the recovery of soil quality and health.

4.01.P-Mo337 Amplicon Sequencing Reveals Active Functionalities in Petroleum-Degrading Microbiome

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Bioremediation of a heavily polluted soil with varying fractions of hydrocarbons ranging from n-C8 to n-C40 was investigated. Total petroleum hydrocarbons (TPH) concentrations were 490,631 mg kg⁻¹ in the surface (0 – 15 cm), 320,971.60 mg kg⁻¹ at 1 m depth and 81, 434.86 mg kg⁻¹ at 1.5 m depth. Remediation of the oil-polluted site began with site mapping where approximately 2 plots of land (Length = 120; Width = 125) were cordoned off from the massively polluted expanse of land. Prior to remediation proper, samples were taken from different points of the mapped site (4°47'41.1"N 6°51'47.2"E - 4°47'42.4"N 6°51'46.4"E) representing the surface soil (0 – 15cm) and subsurface soil (30cm – 1m and 1m – 2m depth). Unpolluted soil samples were also collected approximately 1000 meters away from the artisanal refining site (4°47'26.3"N 6°53'32.1"E) to serve as reference soil for comparison. Remediation involved making, breaking and re-making of ridges at 2 weeks interval to improve aeration and proper mixing of all components. Microbiome analysis was done using 16S rRNA amplicon sequencing on Illumina MiSeq platform. To determine the core bacteria across the different operational taxonomic units (OTUs) in all polluted samples, only OTUs with at least 20% abundance were screened and selected. At least 7 of the core bacterial classes were found to have a minimum prevalence of 70% and included *Alphaproteobacteria*, *Betaproteobacteria*, *Actinobacteria*, *Acidobacteriia*, *Anaerolineae*, *Gammaproteobacteria* and *Bacilli*. At the family level the core bacteria with minimum prevalence of 70% included *Acetobacteraceae*, *Koribacteraceae*, *Bradyrhizobium*, *Anaerolinaceae*, *Hyphomicrobiaceae*, *Commamonadaceae*, *Burkholderiaceae*, *Alcaligenaceae*, *Sphingomonadaceae*, *Xanthomonadaceae* and *Bacillaceae*. Further investigation of the core microbiome during remediation revealed six bacterial genera had at least 70%